

INFLUENCE OF DIHYDROQUERCITIN ON RESTORATION OF LACTATE CONTENT IN BLOOD IN HIGHLY SKILLED ROWERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342971>

Relevance. Today, the constant growth of sports results in canoeing requires intensification of the athletes' training system. To improve the performance of high-class rowers, the use of biologically active additives is in high demand. As such, dihydroquercetin, which has antioxidant, capillary-protective, anti-inflammatory properties, as well as positively affecting the functioning of the cardiovascular, immune, nervous and respiratory systems, has not been studied.

The purpose of the study is to evaluate the effect of dihydroquercetin on the recovery of lactate levels after physical activity in elite rowers.

Materials and methods. The observation was conducted at the Republican Rowing Federation "Rowing and Canoe" in the village of Tashmore, where athletes of the national teams of Uzbekistan in rowing sports train. To assess the effect of physical activity on the relationship between the intensity of physical activity and the content of blood lactic acid, a gradually increasing standard load was used using the Concept-2 rowing machine. Blood was taken from the earlobe, lactate content was determined using the XPER technology L1 lactometer (Taiwan). The athletes consume dihydroquercetin orally in capsules before breakfast and dinner for 1 month at a dose of 100 mg/day. Testing was carried out on the same athletes before and after a month of dihydroquercetin use. For evaluation the effect of dihydroquercetin on recovery processes, the content of lactic acid was analyzed as a biochemical indicator before and after physical activity every 30 minutes in an interval of 1.5 hours. Tests were carried out on an empty stomach in the morning (between 8.00 -10.00)

Results. After physical activity, the concentration of lactic acid was gradually decreased in athletes regardless of the use of the preparation. Immediately after exercise, before taking the flavonoid, the rowers' lactic acid levels increased by 3.2 times, and after a month of taking dihydroquercetin, by 2.3 times. At 30, 60 minutes of observation, the restoration of the lactic acid content after taking dihydroquercetin in rowers was 2.1 times and 1.4 times, respectively, more effective than before consuming the flavonoid. At the 90th minute of observation, no difference in this indicator was noted. It should be noted that the decrease in the lactic acid level to the value noted at rest before dihydroquercetin consumption occurred at the 90th minute, and after taking the drug - at the 60th minute of observation, i.e. 30 minutes earlier. Thus, judging by the reduction in the recovery time of lactate concentration, the main marker in endurance sports, including rowing, daily consumption of dihydroquercetin by athletes for months leads to an earlier recovery of blood lactate levels after physical exercise, i.e. to an increase in the endurance of athletes compared to the indicators observed in the absence of flavonoid intake by rowers.

Conclusion. Faster rates of decrease in the concentration of the main marker of fatigue - i.e. lactate in the blood after dosed physical exercise in athletes who took dihydroquercetin, indicate an improvement in the endurance and adaptation of the highly qualified rowers, as well as the correct choice and dosage of this flavonoid. Dihydroquercetin can be recommended as a dietary supplement to improve resistance to physical stress for rowers, and possibly athletes of other sports.